

ISic0544

I.Sicily inscription 0544

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

stone

Object

unknown

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance

Found 15 September 1568, during the taking down of the Porta Patitellorum, by the church of S. Antonio

Coordinates

38.117202, 13.363462

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height not recorded cm

Width not recorded cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. M(arcus) Ulpus Italici lib(ertus)
2. Eut[y]chus aram
3. et basim Mercuri
4. pr[ae]ter summam hono
5. rariam pro sevir[a]tu
6. pecunia sua posuit
7. d(ono) d(edit)

Apparatus

Text after CIL + add.p.993

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491769
EDR 138299
EDCS 22000853

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7267+add.p.993 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 47

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